

The Alumni Landscape: A Tracer Study on the Career Trajectory of the School of Arts and Sciences Graduate of San Isidro College

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Type of Paper:

RESEARCH ARTICLE

How to cite this paper:

Tuble J.P. & Taja-on, E. (2024). The Alumni Landscape: A Tracer Study on the Career Trajectory of the School of Arts and Sciences Graduate of San Isidro College. *School of Education Research Journal*, 5(1), 1-14.

Received: June 30, 2024

Accepted: July 10, 2024

Published: November 11, 2024

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the career paths of graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS), offering a detailed look into their employment status and professional growth; by investigating where alumni are working and the nature of their roles, the research aims to bridge the gap between academic programs and the evolving needs of the job market. The study used a descriptive research design to investigate the career paths of SAS graduates. Purposive sampling ensures that the sample includes relevant individuals who can provide rich data, while the research instrument is a modified version of a validated questionnaire. Data was collected through an online survey over five weeks, with 72 alumni respondents. The analysis of the career and employment data reveals that the majority of graduates are employed full-time, with significant representation in various sectors and stable job durations. Challenges in job seeking highlight areas for enhanced support services, while the distribution of job locations demonstrates the graduates' geographical mobility and competitiveness. The income data suggests that the programs prepare students for financially rewarding careers. Moreover, the data also indicates that while graduates feel well-prepared in communication, human relations, and leadership skills, they need to strengthen problem-solving and research skills. Significant differences in skill development underscore the necessity for curriculum adjustments. The majority of graduates view the curriculum as relevant, though a small percentage believe updates are needed. Suggestions for improvement, such as adding technology training and updating major subjects, reflect real-world demands and highlight areas for enhancement to ensure the curriculum remains aligned with industry standards and Quality Assurance principles.

Keywords: *alumni, arts and science graduates, career trajectory, skills development, tracer study*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

A *tracer study* is a research method used to follow up on graduates of educational programs to gather information about their career paths, employment status, and professional achievements (Cohen, 2012). This particular tracer study focuses on graduates of the four (4) programs under the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS), aiming to capture the diverse career trajectories of individuals who have completed the degree in disciplines such as Economics, English, Philosophy, and Theology. By examining the post-graduation experiences of these alumni, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive picture of how the education they received has influenced their career development and success.

The study addresses a critical gap in understanding the current professional landscape of SAS graduates (Hill et al., 2016; Camuyong et al., 2023). Limited information is available on where these graduates are currently employed, the nature of their job roles, and how their careers have progressed since leaving the institution (Tadlas, 2021). This lack of data hinders the ability to evaluate the effectiveness of the school's programs and to identify areas that may need enhancement to better support graduates in achieving their career goals (Hallasgo & Taja-on, 2023).

Conducting this tracer study is essential for several reasons. The study provides invaluable feedback to the SAS regarding the real-world impact of its educational programs, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement. The results will inform curriculum development and help ensure that the programs remain relevant and aligned with the demands of the job market. Additionally, the findings will aid in strengthening the department's career support services and alumni network, fostering stronger connections between the institution and its graduates (Brits & Steyn, 2019; Ole et al., 2021).

This study aims to systematically track and analyze the career trajectories of SAS graduates. By collecting and examining data on their professional experiences, the study seeks to identify patterns and trends that can inform future educational strategies and support services.

Conceptual Framework

This tracer study is anchored on the concept of Quality Assurance (QA), which is fundamental to maintaining and enhancing the standards of educational programs. QA encompasses systematic monitoring and evaluation processes to ensure that educational offerings meet established standards and fulfill their intended outcomes (Badiru & Wahome, 2016). By applying QA principles, this study seeks to evaluate the career trajectories of graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS) to ensure that the programs are effectively preparing students for the workforce. The focus on QA aligns with the study's objective to gather empirical data on graduate outcomes, which can then be used to refine and improve the curriculum, thereby ensuring that it remains relevant and responsive to the evolving demands of the job market.

Figure 1.

Schematic diagram of the study

The schematic diagram, as presented in Figure 1, of this study illustrates the interplay between various independent and dependent variables. The diagram exhibits how data on employment status, employability, skills, and competencies developed during their education are collected and analyzed (Hallasgo & Taja-on, 2023). This framework will form the basis for providing feedback and suggestions for curriculum improvement, ensuring that the educational programs offered by SAS align with industry requirements and graduate expectations (Cuadra et al., 2019).

The interplay of the schematic diagrams is deeply rooted in the concept of quality assurance, which seeks to improve educational outcomes continuously. The study underscores the importance of gathering comprehensive data to assess and enhance educational quality. This QA-driven approach ensures that the feedback loop is completed; the findings from the tracer study will directly inform curriculum adjustments and program enhancements (Martin, 2018). Thus, the study not only tracks graduates' career trajectories but also systematically uses this information to uphold and elevate the standards of the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS), ensuring sustained relevance and excellence in its educational offerings.

Statement of the Problem

This study investigated the post-graduation trajectories of graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS) programs at San Isidro College (SIC) between 2011-2012 and 2022-2023. It aimed to identify career paths pursued by graduates and explore how these findings can inform the improvement of SAS programs in light of the K-12 curriculum reforms. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the career trajectory of the SAS graduates?
2. What is the rating of the SAS graduates on their graduate skills?
3. What are the suggestions of the SAS graduates towards the improvement of the curriculum?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employs a descriptive research design (Siedlecki, 2020) to systematically investigate the career trajectories of graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences. The design is appropriate as it allows for a detailed and accurate depiction of the current employment status, employability, and skill sets of alumni without manipulating variables. Descriptive research is well-suited for this study's objectives, as it focuses on collecting factual data and providing a clear, comprehensive picture of the graduates' professional outcomes.

Sample, Sampling Technique, and Research Instrument

The study utilizes a purposive sampling technique (Campbell et al., 2020) to select participants who can provide the most relevant and informative data regarding the career trajectories of graduates. The technique involves deliberately choosing individuals who have specific characteristics—in this case, graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS) within the specified time frame. Purposive sampling is most appropriate for this study because it ensures that the sample includes individuals who have directly experienced the educational programs being evaluated, thereby providing rich and pertinent data for analysis.

The primary research instrument for this study is a modified version of the questionnaire developed by Tadlas (2021). The original questionnaire was designed to survey participants' employment status and employability. Modifications were made to include questions that assess alumni graduate skills. This instrument was chosen because it has been previously validated and provides a comprehensive framework for gathering data on key aspects of the graduates' professional experiences. The modifications ensure that the questionnaire fully addresses the specific objectives of this study.

Table 1 presents the detailed breakdown of participation rates by school year, ensuring that the sample is adequately representative of the alumni population.

Table 1.
Graduate respondents from the Academic Years 2012-2023.

Academic Year	No. of Graduates	No. of Respondents	%
2011–2012	11	5	45.5
2012–2013	17	8	47.1
2013–2014	21	9	42.9
2014–2015	21	8	38.1
2015–2016	11	8	72.7
2016–2017	23	7	30.4
2017–2018	16	6	37.5
2018–2019	26	9	34.6
2019–2020	7	3	42.9
2020–2021	4	2	50.0
2021–2022	-	-	-
2022–2023	9	7	77.8

The respondents for this study, as presented in Table 1, are graduates from the SAS from the school years 2011-2012 to 2022-2023, excluding the school year 2021-2022, with at least a 30% participation rate per school year. This selection criterion ensures a substantial representation of graduates over a significant period, providing a robust data set for analysis.

Table 2 details the participation rates for each program, ensuring that the study captures a broad spectrum of graduate experiences.

Table 2.
Graduate respondents per program.

Program	No. of Graduates	No. of Respondents	%
AB–Economics	28	7	25.0
AB–English	22	7	31.8
AB–Philosophy	100	52	52.0
AB–Theology	16	6	37.5
Total	166	72	43.4

Further, the study surveyed the graduates from the Bachelor of Arts programs in Economics, English, Philosophy, and Theology, with at least a 25% participation rate from each program. This participation ensures that the sample includes a diverse range of disciplines within the SAS, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of the career trajectories across different fields of study.

Table 3 presents this demographic information, providing a detailed context for understanding the respondents' backgrounds and current statuses.

Table 3.
Demographic profile of the School of Arts and Sciences graduates (N=72)

Demographic Profile		f	%
Sex	Male	62	86.11
	Female	10	13.89
Civil Status	Single	34	47.22
	Married	38	52.78
Educational Background	Bachelor's Degree	52	72.22
	Master's Student	14	19.44
	Master's Degree	5	6.95
	Doctorate Student	1	1.39
	Doctorate Degree	-	-

The respondents are distributed as follows: 86.11% are male, reflecting the program's focus on seminarians, and 13.89% are female. Marital status is nearly evenly split, with 47.22% single and 52.78% married. In terms of educational attainment, 72.22% hold bachelor's degrees, 14% are currently master's students, 6.95% have earned master's degrees, and 1.39% are doctorate students.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data gathering for this study involved obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring data privacy, and emphasizing voluntary participation (Dunn & Jeste, 2001). The data collection process spanned five weeks and utilized an online survey method (Van Selm & Jankowski, 2006) to reach a wide range of graduates efficiently. The online survey allowed for broad participation while maintaining the anonymity and confidentiality of respondents, which is crucial for ethical research practices.

In addition to the online survey, follow-up reminders were sent to potential participants to enhance response rates and ensure a representative sample. The comprehensive data collection approach ensured that the study gathered detailed and reliable information on the graduates' career trajectories, providing a solid foundation for analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis

The study employs descriptive statistics to analyze the data gathered from the alumni, offering a clear and detailed summary of their employment status, employability, and skill sets. Additionally, ANOVA was used to compare the graduate skills evaluated by the participants, allowing for a rigorous analysis of differences and patterns among various groups. This combination of statistical methods ensures that the data is thoroughly examined, providing robust insights into the career trajectories of the graduates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Career Trajectory

Table 4 presents the overview of the occupational status of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 4.
Occupational status of the graduates (N=72)

Occupational status		f	%
Employed	Employed	49	68.06
	Employed (enrolled in a postgraduate program)	6	8.33
Unemployed	Unemployed	7	9.72
	Unemployed (actively seeking employment)	0	0.00
	Unemployed (enrolled in a postgraduate program)	1	1.39
Enrolled in a priesthood formation program		8	11.11
Priest		1	1.39

The result, as presented in Table 4, indicates that 76.39% of graduates are employed, with 8.33% employed while enrolled in a graduate program. Additionally, 11.11% are unemployed, and 1.39% are pursuing further education. Furthermore, 11.11% of participants are enrolled in a priest formation program, and 1.39% are ordained priests. These findings indicate a high employment rate among graduates by demonstrating the effectiveness of educational programs in preparing students for diverse career paths (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020). The inclusion of those pursuing further studies and religious vocations highlights the versatility and adaptability of the graduates.

Table 5 presents the summary of the eligibility earned by the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 5.
Eligibility earned by the graduates (N=72)

Eligibility	f	%
Licensure Examination for Teacher (LPT)	24	33.33
Civil Service Eligibility - Non-Professional (CSC-Non Prof)	15	20.83
Civil Service Eligibility - Professional (CSC-Prof)	10	13.89
Napolcom exam	1	1.39

Table 5 details that 33.33% of graduates have passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers, 20.83% have non-professional civil service eligibility, 13.89% have professional civil service eligibility, and 1.39% have passed the Napolcom exam. This high percentage of eligibility earned reflects the programs' alignment with professional standards and requirements. These results indicate that the curriculum effectively equips students with the necessary knowledge and skills to

pass various certification exams, which is a testament to the quality and relevance of the educational offerings (Mina et al., 2020).

Table 6 presents the reason for unemployment of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 6.
Reason of unemployment of the graduates (N=8)

Reason for Unemployment	f	%
Advance or further study	1	12.5
Family Concern and decided not to find a job	3	37.5
Health related reason(s)	1	12.5
Lack of work experience	1	12.5
No job opportunity	1	12.5
Lack of work experience	1	12.5

Table 6 presents the reasons for unemployment among graduates, which include enrollment in further studies, family concerns, health-related issues, lack of work experience, and no job opportunities. These reasons suggest that unemployment is not primarily due to inadequacies in educational programs but rather personal circumstances or external factors (Albina & Sumagaysay, 2020; Castilla et al., 2022). The result underscores the importance of continuous support and career guidance as part of the Quality Assurance framework, helping graduates navigate these challenges and find suitable employment.

Table 7 presents the overview of the employment status of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 7.
Employment status of the graduates (N=55)

Employment Status	f	%
Full-Time	51	92.73
Part-Time	1	1.82
Contractual/Freelance	3	5.45

Table 7 indicates that 92.73% of respondents are employed full-time, 1.82% part-time, and 5.45% in contractual or freelance work. The high rate of full-time employment suggests that the graduates are finding stable positions in the job market, which supports the effectiveness of the academic programs under the Quality Assurance framework. Ensuring that graduates secure full-time positions is a critical indicator of the success and impact of the education provided (Ole et al., 2021; Asoy et al., 2024).

Table 8 presents the summary of the difficulties encountered by the graduates when seeking for employment.

Table 8.
Difficulties encountered by the graduates when seeking for employment (N=34)

Difficulties	f	%
Few job vacancies / lack of position or item	20	54.05
Inadequate experience	5	13.51
Mismatch of educational qualifications	2	5.41
Personality factors	3	8.11
Passing the pre-employment interview	2	5.41
Not meeting paper requirement/s	3	8.11
Others	2	5.41

Table 8 highlights the difficulties graduates face when seeking employment, including few job vacancies, inadequate experience, educational qualification mismatch, personality factors, passing pre-employment interviews, and failing to meet paper requirements. These challenges reflect areas where SAS can enhance its support services, such as offering more robust career counseling and skills development workshops (Meñez, 2014; Lannu & Nobleza, 2017). Addressing these issues ensures that the institution continually improves its programs and student support mechanisms to better prepare graduates for the job market (Hallasgo & Taja-on, 2023).

Table 9 presents overview of the current line of work of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 9.
Line of work of the graduates (N=56)

Line of Work	f	%
Agricultural Industry	1	1.79
Campus Ministry	1	1.79
Law Enforcement	2	3.57
Managerial Position	3	5.36
Office Staff	27	48.21
Priest	1	1.79
Sales Representative	5	8.93
Teaching	16	28.57

The results, as presented in Table 9, show that graduates are employed across various sectors: 1.79% in agriculture, 1.79% in campus ministry, 3.57% in law enforcement, 5.36% in managerial positions, 48.21% as office staff, 1.79% as priests, 8.93% as sales representatives, and 28.57% in teaching. This diverse distribution demonstrates the broad applicability of the skills and knowledge gained from SAS programs. The varied career paths affirm that the curriculum is versatile and prepares students for multiple industries (Asoy et al., 2024).

Table 10 presents the summary of the duration of the graduates in their current job of the SAS programs.

Table 10.
Duration of the graduates in their current job (N=55)

Duration	f	%
Less than a month	5	9.09
1 to 6 months	4	7.27
7 to 11 months	6	10.91
1 year to less than 2 years	15	27.27
2 years to less than 3 years	8	14.55
3 years to less than 4 years	9	16.36
4 years and beyond	8	14.55

Table 10 details the duration graduates have spent in their current jobs: 9.09% for less than a month, 7.27% for 1-6 months, 10.91% for 7-11 months, 27.27% for 1-<2 years, 14.55% for 2-<3 years, 16.36% for 3-<4 years, and 14.55% for 4 years and beyond. The significant percentage of graduates with extended job durations indicates job stability and satisfaction, which are key indicators of successful career preparation and alignment with industry needs (Granovetter, 2018). The stability reflects the commitment to producing well-prepared and adaptable graduates.

Table 11 presents demarcation of the job location of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 11.
Job location of the graduates (N=55)

Job Location	f	%
Within Bukidnon	31	56.36
Within Mindanao	16	29.09
Within the Philippines	7	12.73
Abroad	1	1.82

The analysis of Table 11 reveals that 56.36% of graduates work within Bukidnon, 29.09% within Mindanao, 12.73% elsewhere in the Philippines, and 1.82% abroad. This distribution shows that while most graduates remain local, a considerable number find opportunities beyond their immediate region, reflecting the geographical mobility and competitiveness of the graduates. These results suggest that the programs not only meet local needs but also equip students with the skills necessary to compete in broader job markets (Granovetter, 2018).

Table 12 presents the overview of the initial gross income of the graduates of the SAS programs.

Table 12.
Initial gross income of the graduates (N=55)

Initial Gross Income	f	%
₱ 5,000 to less than ₱ 10,000.00	3	5.45
₱ 10,000 to less than ₱ 15,000.00	10	18.18
₱ 15,000 to less than ₱ 20,000.00	14	25.45
₱ 20,000 to less than ₱ 25,000.00	10	18.18
₱ 25,000.00 and above	18	32.73

Table 12 shows the initial gross income of respondents, with 5.45% earning between ₱ 5,000.00 and ₱ 10,000.00, 18.18% earning between ₱ 10,000.00 and ₱ 15,000.00, 25.45% earning

The Alumni Landscape: A Tracer Study on the Career Trajectory of the School of Arts and Sciences Graduate of San Isidro College

between ₱ 15,000.00 and ₱ 20,000.00, 18.18% earning between ₱ 20,000.00 and ₱ 25,000.00, and 32.73% earning above ₱ 25,000.00. These income levels suggest that a significant portion of graduates are securing well-paying jobs, which is an important outcome for evaluating the success of academic programs (Errighi et al., 2016; Beam & Quimbo, 2021; Roberto et al., 2022). The result indicates that the programs effectively prepare students for financially rewarding careers.

Curricular Program Development of the Graduates

Table 13 presents the summary of the alumna assessment on their graduate skills.

Table 13.
Alumna assessment on their graduate skills.

Graduate Skill	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Int.
Communication Skill	3.41	1.362	A great extent
Human Relation Skill	3.42	1.369	A great extent
Leadership Skill	3.40	1.367	A great extent
Problem Solving Skill	3.25	1.343	A moderate extent
Research Skill	3.23	1.381	A moderate extent

Table 13 reveals that graduates assessed their skills in communication, human relations, and leadership as having been developed to a great extent. In contrast, problem-solving and research skills were developed to a moderate extent. This disparity highlights a potential area for curricular improvement, emphasizing the need to strengthen the development of problem-solving and research skills (Kalaw, 2019). These findings suggest that while the curriculum effectively nurtures interpersonal and leadership abilities (Chen & Rybak, 2017; Abana et al., 2021), it must be adjusted to better equip students with critical analytical and research competencies essential for professional success (Ulger, 2018).

Table 14 presents the comparison of the graduate skills of the alumni.

Table 14.
Comparison of the graduate skills

Graduate Skill	Mean	F	p
Communication Skill	3.41 a		
Human Relation Skill	3.42 a		
Leadership Skill	3.40 a	17.554	0.022*
Problem Solving Skill	3.25 b		
Research Skill	3.23 b		

NOTE: *-significant at 0.05

As presented in Table 14, the f-value of the five (5) graduate skills is 17.554 and a p-value of 0.022 (p<0.05), indicating that there is a significant difference between the five (5) graduate skills. Additionally, Table 14 illustrates that the skill on communication, human relationship, and leadership have a higher level as compared to problem solving and research. This significant variation underscores the need for targeted interventions to elevate the development of problem-solving and research competencies. These results highlight the importance of evaluating and refining the curriculum to address disparities and enhance overall educational outcomes (Ulger, 2018; Kalaw, 2019). The significant differences in skill development suggest that while graduates are confident in their communication and leadership abilities, they may face challenges in more

technical aspects, such as problem-solving and research. Addressing this imbalance through curriculum adjustments will ensure a more comprehensive skill set for graduates, which will aim to provide a balanced and effective educational experience.

Table 15 presents the evaluation of the graduates on the relevance of the curriculum.

Table 15.
Evaluation of the graduates on the relevance of the curriculum (N=72)

Relevance	f	%
Yes	65	90.28
No	7	9.72

Table 15 indicates that 90.28% of alumni view the curriculum as relevant, while 9.72% consider it no longer relevant. The high percentage of perceived relevance suggests that the majority of graduates find their education applicable to their current professional roles. However, the minority who view the curriculum as outdated points to areas that may require updates to maintain its applicability. These results emphasize the need for regular curriculum reviews and updates to ensure it meets evolving industry standards and graduate needs.

Suggestions Towards the Improvement of the Curriculum

Matrix 1 summarizes the suggestions from the graduates towards the improvement of the curriculum.

Matrix 1.
Suggestions from the graduates towards the curriculum.

Suggestion	Sample Statement
Add training on Technology	<i>“Add subjects/training about electronic literacy such as, Excel, PowerPoint, Microsoft word, Photoshop etc...”</i>
Curriculum Updating	<i>“Always update the curriculum with the latest trends in education”</i>
Intensify Major Subject	<i>“...explore more in contemporary philosophers (not just in ancient, medieval and modern/postmodern philosophers) ...”</i>
Subjects to Prepare for Teaching	<i>“...provide education subjects that would prepare philo majors in teaching (since majority will be engaged in teaching). Aside from that, one of the aims of philosophy is to allow the philo majors to teach others on how to think critically, that is why units in education is necessary...”</i>

Matrix 1 presents various suggestions from graduates for curriculum improvement, including adding training on technology, updating the curriculum, intensifying major subjects, and incorporating subjects to prepare for teaching. These suggestions are drawn from graduates' real-life experiences and reflect their insights into the skills and knowledge required in the current job market. The recommendation to add training on technology indicates a recognition of the growing importance of digital literacy and technological skills in the workplace (Tomaro, 2018). Updating the curriculum and intensifying major subjects reflect the need for in-depth knowledge and expertise in specific fields, ensuring that graduates are well-prepared for their professional roles (Aquino & Jalagat, 2021). Including subjects to prepare for teaching suggests that many graduates pursue careers in education and feel the need for more targeted preparation in this area (Alda et al., 2020).

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The results present a detailed view of the employment and career trajectories of graduates from the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS). The data reveal that a majority of graduates are employed, with some also enrolled in graduate programs, while some of the graduates are unemployed. A notable portion of graduates has achieved various professional eligibilities, such as the Licensure Examination for Teachers and civil service exams. The reasons for unemployment include further studies, family concerns, health issues, lack of experience, and limited job opportunities. The majority of employed graduates hold full-time positions, with some working part-time or on a contractual basis. Challenges in job seeking include few vacancies, inadequate experience, and mismatched qualifications.

Moreover, the results provide insights into the specific fields and employment characteristics of the graduates. Graduates are predominantly employed in office staff roles and teaching positions, with others in various sectors, such as sales, management, and law enforcement. The duration in their current jobs varies, with many holding their positions for one to less than two years. Employment locations are mainly within Bukidnon and Mindanao, with a small percentage working abroad. Initial gross income levels are varied, with the largest group earning 25,000 pesos and above, indicating a range of financial outcomes post-graduation.

Furthermore, the results focus on the graduates' assessment of their skills and the relevance of the curriculum. Graduates rated their communication, human relations, and leadership skills as highly developed while problem-solving and research skills were moderately developed. Statistical analysis showed significant differences in the development levels of these skills. Most alumni find the curriculum relevant, though a minority see it as outdated. Suggestions for improvement include enhancing technology training, updating curriculum content, intensifying major subjects, and adding teaching preparation courses, reflecting a need to align the curriculum more closely with current professional requirements.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that SAS undertake a comprehensive curriculum review to incorporate more robust training in problem-solving and research skills. Integrating advanced technology courses and updating existing course content will ensure that the curriculum remains relevant and responsive to industry changes. Additionally, intensifying major subjects and providing targeted preparation for teaching careers will better equip graduates for their professional paths. Enhancing support services for job placement and addressing the specific challenges identified by graduates, such as the mismatch of qualifications and inadequate experience, will further bolster the graduates' employability and career success.

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